

Investigation of the Water Detection Performance of the Water-In-Fuel (WIF) Sensor in Diesel Fuel

Erdal Kılıç^{1,∅}, Ertuğrul Karakulak^{2,+}, Ersoy Mevsim^{3,*}, and Reşat Mutlu^{4,¥}

¹Vocational School of Technical Sciences, Agricultural Machinery Department, Tekirdag Namik Kemal University, Tekirdag, Türkiye, 59030.

²Electronics Department, Vocational school of Technical Sciences, Tekirdağ Namik Kemal University, Tekirdag, Türkiye, 59030.

³Department of Computer Technologies, Vocational school of Technical Sciences, Tekirdağ Namik Kemal University, Tekirdag, Türkiye, 59030.

⁴Department of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department, Faculty of Çorlu Engineering, Tekirdağ Namik Kemal University, Tekirdağ, Türkiye, 59860.

To cite this article:

Erdal Kılıç, Ertuğrul Karakulak, Reşat Mutlu, and Ersoy Mevsim. “Investigation of the Water Detection Performance of the Water-In-Fuel (WIF) Sensor in Diesel Fuel”, *Parana Journal of Science and Education*. Vol. 11, No. 6, 2025, pp. 17-22.

Received: October 26, 2025; **Accepted:** November 17, 2025; **Published:** December 1, 2025.

Abstract

In diesel engine systems, water in the fuel is one of the main pollutants that adversely affect the performance of the engine and the life of its components. In this study, the sensing performance of Water-in-Fuel (WIF) sensors for diesel fuel engines was investigated in solutions of water with different ratios of ethylene glycol and water mixtures and at varying water hardness levels. As the water hardness increased, the sensor output voltage decreased; at hardnesses above 3°F, no water warning was obtained from the sensor. WIF sensors lose sensitivity at high glycol ratios (70% and above) due to low conductivity, and at mixtures above 80%, the water warning from the sensor is either very short or does not occur at all. This indicates that the sensor can only detect soft water. The results showed that the efficiency of the sensor varies depending on the conductivity of the water and the mixing properties.

Keywords: Diesel engine, Water-in-Fuel sensor, WIF sensor, sensor performance, water contamination, ethylene glycol, water hardness, fuel pollution, conductivity, sensor sensitivity, soft water detection, engine protection .

[∅] Email: ekilic@nku.edu.tr

⁺ Email: ekarakulak@nku.edu.tr

^{*} Email: emevsim@nku.edu.tr

[¥] Email: rmutlu@nku.edu.tr (Corresponding Author)

1. Introduction

Diesel engines are widely used as a power source in many sectors such as electricity generation, marine, land, and railway transportation due to their high thermal efficiency and fuel economy advantages. However, diesel fuel systems—especially high-precision Common Rail Injection (CRI) systems [1] are highly sensitive to the presence of water in the fuel. Water in the fuel can cause corrosion, wear, reduced lubrication, and serious degradation in the engine's operating performance [2]. Today's commonly used modern CRI systems operate at very high injection pressures exceeding 300 MPa. Achieving such pressure levels necessitates minimizing aggressive components in the fuel in order to maintain the chemical stability of the metal alloys used in engine systems. Therefore, the long-term, safe operation of the system is only possible through strictly defined fuel specifications. Water present in diesel fuel can cause significant damage to fuel system components that operate with high precision, especially in next-generation engines [2, 3]. The presence of water in any fuel source leads to a noticeable decrease in both exhaust gas temperature and heat release rate. This causes irregularities in ignition and combustion processes, negatively affecting engine performance, and may particularly result in a reduction in torque output [4,5]. Timely analysis of quality parameters of petroleum products is important for their safe and effective use across various industries. Environmental factors such as ambient temperature, pressure, and storage conditions can increase the moisture content of the products, adversely affecting their quality [6]. For this reason, the EN 590 standard [7] limits the maximum water content in diesel fuel to 200 mg/kg and recommends the use of the Coulometric Karl Fischer titration method for determining this parameter [5, 6]. This method enables highly accurate detection of water content in diesel fuel within the range of 0.003% to 0.100%. Moreover, the solubility limit of water in diesel fuel is quite low. For example, at 40°C, the amount of dissolved water is only around 100 ppm. This low solubility threshold facilitates the formation of free water phase, thereby increasing the risk of corrosion and failure in the system [8, 9]. Various detection systems are used in engines to identify free water or fuel-water emulsions. These systems perform measurements based on the electrical resistance and conductivity properties of free water, the dielectric characteristics of emulsions, or differences in the refractive index of the fluid [10, 11]. Due to their low cost, detection of water in fuel in thermal

engines is generally carried out using electrical resistance measurements. These sensors are placed at the bottom of the fuel filter, a point where water accumulates due to density differences before it reaches the engine. The amount of water is detected via electrical resistance measurements, using Water-in-Fuel (WIF) sensors. Due to the integrated structure of thermal engines and the presence of multiple systems together, it is possible for water of varying hardness or antifreeze mixtures of various ratios to be introduced into the fuel. However, to date, no study has been found in the literature examining the performance of Water-in-Fuel sensors—which operate based on electrical resistance measurements—in detecting water with different hardness levels and antifreeze mixtures. In this study, a Water-in-Fuel (WIF) sensor from a 1.5 DCI diesel engine of the Renault brand was tested with waters of different hardness levels and antifreezes at various concentrations, and the results are presented. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the principles and operational characteristics of Water-in-Fuel sensors. Section 3 presents the experimental study, including sensor response in water–ethylene glycol mixtures and the influence of water hardness on WIF sensor behavior. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper with a summary of findings and recommendations for future research and sensor development.

2. WIF (Water-in-Fuel) Sensors

WIF sensors are typically placed at the bottom of fuel filter water separators in diesel fuel systems. The sensor operates based on the principle of conductivity difference between two electrodes, detecting the water that accumulates at the bottom of the filter housing due to density differences. When the water level reaches a certain threshold, the WIF sensor generates a logic-1 output. This signal is detected by the ECU (Engine Control Unit), which then triggers a warning signal. The purpose of this system is to alert the user before the water reaches the fuel injection system. In this study, a WIF sensor from a Renault brand 1.5 DCI diesel engine was used. A photo of the sensor is shown in Figure 1. The WIF sensor used is integrated with the diesel fuel filter in the diesel vehicle. As shown in Figure 1, the Electrode Contact Points extend to the bottom of the filter. Due to the difference in density, water in the diesel fuel accumulates at the bottom of the filter. The electrical resistance

measurement of the WIF sensor takes place at this point. A simplified circuit diagram of the system connected behind the sensor is shown below in Figure (2). The circuit shown in Figure 1 was reconstructed exactly as taken from the vehicle's original wiring diagrams. In the circuit, the LM358 integrated circuit functions as a voltage follower, and the output voltage of the voltage follower drives the BD139, an NPN transistor. When this transistor conducts, a logic signal is sent to the ECU to indicate that water has been detected. The LED is used for visualization of whether the logic signal exists or water has been detected.

Figure 1: Structure of the WIF sensor.

Source: Authors.

Figure 2: The WIF sensor and its circuit.

Source: Authors.

3. Experimental Results

During the experimental studies, water with different hardness levels and various mixtures of water and ethylene glycol (antifreeze) were used with the WIF sensor. The relevant mixtures were tested using the circuit setup shown in Figure (2).

3.1 Sensor Response in Water–Ethylene Glycol Mixtures

Mixtures of water and ethylene glycol-based antifreeze (commercial name: Glaceol RX Type D) were prepared in different ratios. For each mixture, the freezing point, the sensor output voltage (in mV) measured from the op-amp output, and whether water was detected by the system were observed.

While recording the values shown in Table (1), the freezing points of different antifreeze mixtures were also measured and added to the table. For each mixture, the output voltage from the sensor was recorded. The sensor failed to detect pure water and antifreeze mixtures with high glycol content, or had difficulty in detecting them. Figure 3 shows the graph of the WIF sensor output voltage variation according to the water–glycol mixture ratio.

Figure 3: Variation of WIF Sensor Output Voltage According to Water–Glycol Mixture

Source: Authors.

Table 1. Sensor Behavior Based on Water–Glycol Ratio

Water–Glycol Ratio (%)	Freezing Point (°C)	Output Voltage (mV)	Sensor Detection
100 Water	0	92	Not Detected
90% Water 10% Glycol	-4	615	Detected
80% Water 20% Glycol	-9	660	Detected
70% Water 30% Glycol	-16	654	Detected
60% Water 40% Glycol	-25	584	Detected
50% Water 50% Glycol	-33	676	Detected
40% Water 60% Glycol	-47	690	Detected
30% Water 70% Glycol	<-50	690	Detected
20% Water 80% Glycol	<-50	93	Detected for 0.5 sec
10% Water 90% Glycol	<-50	93	Brief detection
100% Glycol	<-50	100	Not Detected
Control (Air)	-	93	Not Detected

Source: Authors.

In mixtures containing more than 70% glycol, a decrease in sensor effectiveness began, and when the glycol content dropped below 80%, the LED signal weakened. At 100% glycol, the sensor did not respond at all. Although the LED remained on in mixtures above 70% glycol, the voltage output stabilized. The sensor’s detection capability weakened in glycol concentrations of 80% and above. Accordingly, it is understood that the WIF sensor does not detect every ratio of antifreeze mixed into diesel fuel in the same way.

3.2 WIF Sensor Response to Water Hardness

Different hardness levels of water were obtained by adding calcium carbonate to 100 milliliters of pure water according to the French hardness degree (°F). The effect of waters prepared by adding certain amounts of calcium carbonate to pure water at different French hardness degrees on the sensor was evaluated. The response of the WIF sensor to waters with different hardness levels is given in Table (2).

Table 2. Output Voltage and Sensor Detection Status According to Water Hardness Levels

Hardness Level (°F)	Output Voltage (mV)	Sensor Detection
1	740	Detected
2	670	Detected
3	560	Not Detected
4	520	Not Detected
5	510	Not Detected
6	540	Not Detected
7	540	Not Detected
8	540	Not Detected
9	540	Not Detected
10	540	Not Detected

Source: Authors.

As seen in Table (2), waters with hardness levels between 3 and 10 were not detected by the WIF sensor system, while waters with hardness levels between 1 and 2 were detected. Figure 4 shows the graph of the change in WIF sensor output voltage according to water hardness variation.

Figure 4. Graph of WIF Sensor Output Voltage vs. Water Hardness

Source: Authors.

It was observed that as water hardness increased, the sensor's detection capacity decreased. The sensor was only able to give warnings at low hardness levels (°F 1–2). Only waters with low hardness levels could be detected by the sensor.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the performance of WIF sensors used to detect water in diesel fuel—a significant issue in diesel engine systems—was experimentally evaluated using various ratios of water-ethylene glycol mixtures and waters with different hardness levels. The findings are summarized below:

- WIF sensors operate with high sensitivity in liquids with high conductivity (especially pure water and mixtures with low glycol content), but a significant decrease in detection capacity was observed when the glycol ratio exceeded 70%.
- In mixtures containing 80% or more glycol, the sensor's LED warning was either very brief or did not occur at all. This indicates that low-conductivity liquids like glycol push the WIF sensors to their operational limits.
- As water hardness increased, the sensor output voltage decreased, and no LED warning was received starting from a hardness of 3 °F. This shows that the sensors can effectively detect only soft water.

Modern common rail diesel injection systems have very low tolerances, and even minimal amounts of water in the fuel can cause serious damage to these systems. Therefore, the limited detection capacity of current WIF sensors poses a potential risk for engine systems. It is clear that WIF sensors need not only to detect the presence of water but also to develop a discriminative sensitivity against different types of contaminants. In this regard, equipping sensor technology with a multi-parameter structure (for example: conductivity + density + temperature) will enable the development of more reliable detection and prevention systems. Filter design should be restructured not only to separate particles but also to remove condensed liquid water more quickly and effectively. The findings of this study can be effectively integrated into the training of students preparing to work in fields that utilize WIF sensors, such as automotive and agricultural machinery repair workshops.

References

- [1] Nikzadfar K., Shamekhi A. H. More than one decade with development of common-rail diesel engine management systems: a literature review on modelling, control, estimation and calibration. *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part D: J. Automob. Eng.*, 229(8), pp. 1110–1142 (2015).
- [2] Sarvi A., Kilpinen P., Zevenhoven R. Emissions from large-scale medium-speed diesel engines: 3. Influence of direct water injection and common rail. *Fuel Process. Technol.*, 90(2), pp. 222–231 (2009).
- [3] Bertola A., Li R., Boulouchos K. Influence of water-diesel fuel emulsions and EGR on combustion and exhaust emissions of heavy duty DI-diesel engines equipped with common-rail injection system. *SAE Trans.*, pp. 2244–2260 (2003).
- [4] Awad O. I., Mamat R., Ibrahim T. K., Ali O. M., Kadrigama K., Leman A. Performance and combustion characteristics of an SI engine fueled with fusel oil-gasoline at different water content. *Appl. Therm. Eng.*, 123, pp. 1374–1385 (2017).
- [5] Demirbas A. Relationships between Heating Value and Lignin, Moisture, Ash and

- Extractive Contents of Biomass Fuels. *Energy Explor. Exploit.*, 20, pp. 105–111 (2002).
- [6] Latarche M. *Pounder's Marine Diesel Engines and Gas Turbines*. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann, p. — (2020).
- [7] Arouni H., et al. Limitations of monoolein in simulating water-in-fuel characteristics of EN590 diesel containing biodiesel in water separation testing. *SAE Int. J. Fuels Lubr.*, 11(3), pp. 229–238 (2018).
- [8] Van Gerpen J., Hammond E., Yu L., Monyem A. Determining the Influence of Contaminants on Biodiesel Properties. *SAE Tech. Paper No. 971685*, p. — (1997).
- [9] Macioszek Ł., Rybski R. Evaluation of Water Content in Diesel Fuel Using Impedance Spectroscopy. *XXI IMEKO World Congress "Measurement in Research and Industry"*, August 30 – September 4, Prague, Czech Republic (2015).
- [10] David J. I., Robert M. N. *Engineering Circuit Analysis International Students Version*, 10th Edition. Wiley Publishers, USA (2010).
- [11] Uche R., Augustine A. Design and Development of Water-In-Fuel Detector. *Innovative Systems Design and Engineering*, Vol. 3, No. 10, ISSN 2222-1727 (Paper), ISSN 2222-2871 (Online) (2012).